

Foundations of Adaptor Signatures

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Abstract. Adaptor signatures extend the functionality of regular signatures through the computation of *pre-signatures* on messages for statements of NP relations. Pre-signatures are publicly verifiable; they simultaneously hide and commit to a signature of an underlying signature scheme on that message. Anybody possessing a corresponding witness for the statement can adapt the pre-signature to obtain the “regular” signature. Adaptor signatures have found numerous applications for conditional payments in blockchain systems, like payment channels (CCS’20, CCS’21), private coin mixing (CCS’22, SP’23), and oracle-based payments (NDSS’23).

In our work, we revisit the state of the security of adaptor signatures and their constructions. In particular, our two main contributions are:

- **Security Gaps and Definitions:** We review the widely-used security model of adaptor signatures due to Aumayr *et al.* (AC’21) and identify gaps in their definitions that render known protocols for private coin-mixing and oracle-based payments *insecure*. We give simple counterexamples of adaptor signatures that are secure w.r.t. their definitions but result in insecure instantiations of these protocols. To fill these gaps, we identify a minimal set of modular definitions that align with these practical applications.
- **Secure Constructions:** Despite their popularity, *all* known constructions are (1) derived from identification schemes via the Fiat-Shamir transform in the random oracle model or (2) require modifications to the underlying signature verification algorithm, thus making the construction useless in the setting of cryptocurrencies. More concerningly, *all* known constructions were proven secure w.r.t. the insufficient definitions of Aumayr *et al.*, leaving us with no provably secure adaptor signature scheme to use in applications.

Firstly, in this work, we salvage *all* current applications by proving the security of the widely-used Schnorr adaptor signatures under our proposed definitions. We then provide several new constructions, including presenting the *first* adaptor signature schemes for Camenisch-Lysyanskaya (CL), Boneh-Boyen-Shacham (BBS+), and Waters signatures, all of which are proven secure *in the standard model*. Our new constructions rely on a new abstraction of digital

signatures, called *dichotomic signatures*, which covers the essential properties we need to build adaptor signatures. Proving the security of all constructions (including identification-based schemes) relies on a *novel non-black-box* proof technique. Both our digital signature abstraction and the proof technique could be of independent interest to the community.

Keywords: Enhanced Signatures · Adaptor Signatures · Non-black Box Reduction · BBS+ · CL · Waters+ · Schnorr · Standard Model

1 Introduction

Adaptor signatures allow a signer to compute a verifiable promise w.r.t. some NP statement Y , called a pre-signature. The signer promises that anyone who knows a witness y for Y can compute a correct signature from the pre-signature and otherwise cannot. Adaptor signatures are extractable; given a pre-signature and a signature, one can efficiently extract the witness y . Adaptor signatures have numerous applications in the blockchain space, such as payment channels [15, 27, 16], private coin mixing [21, 29], and oracle-based payments [25], among many others.

Security Definitions. Adaptor signatures were initially defined for the one-time fair exchange of a coin for a witness; now, they serve in various settings that deviate from this two-party fair exchange as outlined above. Given that the security definitions were initially formulated exclusively for one-time fair exchange scenarios, the question arises as to whether the security model has the necessary strength for new applications. Recently, Dai *et al.* [14] revisited the security model and proposed stronger definitions. The authors justify the need for one of their definitions with a contrived counter-example identifying a definitional gap. Unfortunately, this definitional gap remains purely theoretical and is not applicable to novel applications, which brings us back to our original question:

- *Which definitions are both necessary and sufficient for real adaptor signature applications?*

We re-examine the security of adaptor signatures in the context of the new applications and identify multiple vulnerabilities that lead to specific attacks within each application. These attacks have two implications. First, the security proofs of nearly all recent applications have gaps. We illustrate these gaps by creating artificial schemes that maintain security according to the original definitions [17, 3]. However, when our scheme is used in private coin mixing [21, 29] or the oracle-based payments protocol [25], it leads to insecure protocols. Our attacks confirm the necessity for stronger definitions as previously suggested by Dai *et al.* [14]. However, our attacks also reveal that a very basic property is missing to securely realize these applications. We close this gap by introducing *pre-verify soundness*, a property that ensures that the pre-verification algorithm satisfies

(computational) soundness w.r.t. the NP relation Rel. Second, our attacks expose weaknesses in the original security proofs within all practical applications of adaptor signatures, such as private coin mixing [21, 29] and oracle-based payment [25] protocols. However, specific implementations that rely on the Schnorr adaptor signature within the random oracle framework remain unaffected (we prove the security of Schnorr adaptor signatures w.r.t. the stronger definitions within our general framework). This observation underscores that practitioners, when designing innovative applications, prioritize a distinct set of security properties that may not be generically covered by current adaptor signature formalization. Given the rapid development and integration of adaptor signatures in the blockchain domain, there is an urgent need to bridge the gap between intuitively understood security properties and the underlying formal guarantees. To address this, we strive to narrow this gap by extracting a minimal set of modular definitions that align with these practical applications.

Constructions. Adaptor signatures are always defined w.r.t. some underlying *fixed* signature scheme. The underlying signature scheme is typically hardcoded in some blockchain application prohibiting any modification to the scheme itself, especially not the verification algorithm. In other words, any adaptor signature scheme must end up issuing signatures that are verified under the original verification algorithm of the signature scheme. This practical limitation makes the construction of adaptor signatures challenging. It leads to the fact that all known constructions are based on identification schemes that are converted to a signature scheme using the Fiat-Shamir transformation in the Random oracle model [4, 18, 31, 3, 17, 1]. The only exception is the work of Aumayr et al. [3], where they construct an adaptor signature scheme for ECDSA based on concepts from [26]. Unfortunately, the security of *all* known schemes is proven secure only in the model proposed by Aumayr *et al.* [3], which we show is insufficient for novel applications. This leads to an unsatisfactory situation in which practitioners use unproven constructions, and all possible candidate schemes achieve security only within the random oracle model.

Relying on the random oracle model is undesirable for at least two reasons. First, the random oracle model is not sound, as demonstrated by Canetti, Goldreich, and Halevi [13]. Consequently, the pursuit of constructions within the standard model is crucial to instill greater confidence in the existence of this cryptographic primitive in general. Second, using the Fiat-Shamir transformation causes the signature algorithm not to work well in all (practical) applications, such as anonymous credentials, which hinders further adaptation of this primitive. The challenge here is the application of the hash function, which often cannot be (efficiently) integrated into complicated zero-knowledge proofs. Therefore, we put forward the following questions:

- *Does the Schnorr adaptor signature scheme satisfy the stronger security notions?*
- *Given a standard model signature scheme Σ , can we construct a standard model adaptor signature scheme AS based on Σ without modifying Σ ?*

We answer both questions in the affirmative. In particular, we present the first adaptor signatures that do not rely on the random oracle heuristic. Instead of proving security for all schemes from scratch, we develop a general framework, referred to as *dichotomic adaptor signatures*, that covers all known ID-based adaptor signatures and several standard model signature schemes, such as CL signatures [12], the strongly unforgeable Waters signature scheme [8], and the BBS+ [7] signature scheme, which is currently being standardized. When instantiating our framework with the strongly unforgeable Waters signature scheme [8], we obtain the first adaptor signature scheme that is secure under the CDH assumption, one of the weakest cryptographic assumptions used in practice. The security proof includes a novel non-black-box proof technique called *transparent reduction*, which may also be of independent interest to the community.

1.1 Our Contribution

Our contribution can be summarized as follows.

- We show that the initial formal security model for adaptor signatures leads to insecure instances when adaptor signatures are applied in real-world scenarios. To ensure the safe and reliable use of adaptor signatures in practical applications, we extract and simplify the core concepts of the stronger definitions by Dai, Okamoto, and Yamamoto [14] and introduce a missing security property required by the real-world applications, called pre-verify soundness.
- We present the first adaptor signature schemes in the standard model without modifying the signature verification algorithms of the underlying signature schemes; a crucial requirement for practical applications which rely on standardized primitives. Concretely, we design adaptor signature schemes based on the signature schemes of Camenisch and Lysyanskaya (CL) [12], Boneh, Boyen, and Shacham (BBS+) [7] that are widely used in modern digital systems in the context of Anonymous Credentials. Furthermore, we also present an adaptor signature scheme based on the strongly unforgeable Waters signature (Waters+) [8].
- Our third contribution is conceptual. We analyze the algebraic properties of the underlying signature schemes of all known adaptor signatures to find a common blueprint that can then be instantiated in the standard model. We call our resulting abstraction *dichotomic signatures* and show that it covers all known schemes (that lead to current adaptor constructions) as well as the CL, BBS+, and Waters+ signature schemes. Our adaptor signature constructions are highly efficient and add little to no overhead over the algorithms of the underlying signature schemes.
- On a technical level, we present a novel non-black-box proof technique called *transparent reductions*, which exploits the code of a reduction from the signature scheme to the underlying hard problem in a non-black-box way. This technique allows us to formally analyze the security of our adaptor signature schemes based on dichotomic signatures in the standard model, i.e., not relying on the ROM. Since CL, BBS+, and Waters+ are signature schemes in the

standard model (i.e., not relying on the ROM), this gives us the first adaptor signature schemes in the standard model (provided that the signature verification algorithms are not modified). In addition, we show that transparent reductions can also be used to prove the security of Schnorr adaptor signatures. We believe that transparent reductions are indeed necessary to prove standard model adaptor signatures secure: Without the powerful toolset of the random oracle model (namely programming and witness extractable NIZKs), it seems impossible to simulate a pre-signature oracle without violating the strong unforgeability of the underlying signature scheme.

2 Technical Overview

In this section, we give an overview of our contributions towards improving *both* the foundations and the practice of adaptor signatures. Towards this, we begin with a description of the adaptor signature functionality in Section 2.1 and its formalization for the case of payment channels by Aumayr et al. [3]. Then, in Section 2.2, we give an overview of the gaps we identified in the existing security definitions of [3] along with explicit attacks that break the security of *three* higher-level protocols that use adaptor signatures. With these gaps in mind, we advocate the use of the recently introduced security definitions by Dai *et al.* [14] for adaptor signatures. In Section 2.3, we switch focus and present our new general framework for constructing secure adaptor signatures. Finally, in Section 2.4, we discuss several instantiations of our framework, including presenting the *first* adaptor signatures for several signatures schemes, including Boneh-Boyen-Shacham (BBS+) [7]. These instantiations result in the *first* adaptor signatures in the standard model.

2.1 Adaptor Signatures and Payment Channels

We begin by describing the adaptor signature scheme functionality, which was introduced by Poelstra [28]. Informally, an adaptor signature scheme models a blockchain-based protocol for fairly exchanging a digital signature (e.g., on a transaction) and a witness for an NP statement. More specifically, the adaptor signature scheme consists of four algorithms (pSign , pVrfy , Adapt , Extract) which are used as follows for the fair exchange: a signer Alice uses the pre-signing algorithm pSign to compute a pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma}$ on a transaction message m w.r.t. an NP statement Y held by Bob. Then, running the adapt algorithm Adapt on $\tilde{\sigma}$ and its witness y , Bob computes a valid signature σ on the message m under Alice’s signing key. To redeem the payment, Bob posts σ on the blockchain; this allows Alice to learn the witness y by running the extract algorithm Extract on the $(\tilde{\sigma}, \sigma)$ pair. Thus, Alice obtains the witness for the statement Y , while Bob obtains the signature on the transaction message m .

The work of Aumayr *et al.* [3] showed a mechanism to bootstrap the above fair-exchange protocol to enable *payment channels*, a scalability solution for blockchain-based cryptocurrency payments. To formally capture security for

this fair exchange, they proposed *three* essential security properties for adaptor signatures: *unforgeability*, *pre-signature adaptability*, and *witness-extractability*. For the sake of this overview, we will only focus on the property of witness-extractability, which is crucial for fairness. Informally, witness extractability ensures that Alice can successfully extract Bob’s witness from *every* valid signature σ given by Bob. Without witness-extractability, there may exist a valid signature σ , which is sufficient for Bob to redeem the payment, but knowing σ may not allow Alice to learn the witness, thereby violating fairness. To formalize this, Aumayr et al. consider the following game and, for security, require that no efficient adversarial Bob wins the game with non-negligible probability:

- The challenger provides a signing and a pre-signing oracle to Bob.
- Eventually, Bob outputs as challenge a message m^* and a statement Y^* .
- The challenger computes a *single* pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma}$ on (m^*, Y^*) and forwards $\tilde{\sigma}$ to Bob, who again has access to the oracles and eventually outputs a signature forgery σ^* .
- Bob wins if he never asks any of the oracles on the message m^* , and the forgery does not extract with $\tilde{\sigma}$, i.e. $(Y^*, \text{Extract}(\tilde{\sigma}, \sigma^*)) \notin \text{Rel}$.

This formalization of witness extractability, where the adversary only has access to exactly one pre-signature on the challenge message m^* , is meaningful for the payment channel setup, where the messages on which the pre-signatures are computed on are unique transactions. Therefore, the adversary will never learn two pre-signatures on the same message, as each transaction is different and no transaction can be executed twice.

2.2 Gaps in Adaptor Signature Definitions

Our starting point is the observation that the above three properties are specifically tailored to the setting of payment channels. For example, for witness-extractability, it is sufficient that every valid signature on a message m computed by Bob is extractable when Bob has learned exactly one pre-signature on m before. Therefore, a Bob capable of generating a *non-extractable* signature after learning *two* pre-signatures on the same message m does not hurt payment channels. However, as we show next, such a Bob not only exists but also voids the security for adaptor-signature-based protocols beyond payment channels.

Beyond payment channels, adaptor signatures have found more broad applications, such as oracle-based payments [25], and (blind) coin-mixing services [21, 29]. Despite being used in much broader contexts, the security is argued relying on the formalization of adaptor signatures tailored towards the case of payment channels. This mismatch allows us to break the security of all the above three protocols. In particular, for each of these protocols, we find adaptor signature schemes that (a) satisfy the security definitions in [3], but (b) render the higher-level protocol insecure. Henceforth, we refer to such adaptor signature schemes as *counter-examples*.

Counter-examples. The key idea towards designing counter-examples relies on exploiting the differences between the considered protocol’s setting and that of payment channels. For example, for the case of oracle-based payments, we design an adaptor-signature with *leaky pre-signatures*: To build these, we use an adaptor signature scheme that is secure w.r.t. the definitions provided by [3]. To make a pre-signature on a message m leaky, we add a two-out-of-two share of a signature σ on m to the pre-signature. When a party only learns a single pre-signature, this two-out-of-two hides the additional signature σ . However, if one learns a second pre-signature on the same message, the combination of both shares can be used to extract σ . We show later in this overview that if instantiated with adaptor signatures with leaky pre-signatures, the security of oracle-based payments cannot be argued if a single transaction is pre-signed twice. But computing a second pre-signature is a desirable goal for this application.

Similarly, for coin-mixing protocols [21] and blind-coin-mixing protocols [29], we design adaptor signature schemes where pre-signatures satisfy properties of *malleability* and *unadaptability*. We postpone the description of these properties and the constructions to Section 3. We provide a summary of the protocols affected by our attacks in Table 1 and continue with explaining how the class of leaky pre-signatures breaks the one-wayness of oracle-based payments.

Protocol	Pre-Signatures in Our Counter-Examples
Oracle-Based Payments [25]	Leaky (Section 3.1)
Blind Hubs [29]	Unadaptability (Section 3.2)
Coin Mixing [21]	Malleability (Section 3.3)

Table 1: An overview of which protocol is affected by which gap.

Insecurity of Oracle-Based Payments. Oracle-based payments allow two mistrusting parties, Alice and Bob, to make payments conditional on the outcome of some real-world event [25]. To do this, Alice sends verifiably encrypted signatures on transactions to Bob. These encrypted signatures can be decrypted by Bob when a threshold number of semi-trusted oracles sign predetermined messages. For example, if Alice wants to pay Bob 5 coins if the weather is rainy on a given date, she encrypts a signature on a transaction of 5 coins to Bob. If Bob receives the testimony of at least three weather oracles that it rained on the given date, he can decrypt the signature and redeem the payment. Adaptor signatures are used as the main building block for oracle-based payments. The encryption of a signature is a pre-signature that can be verified using the pre-verify algorithm. The pre-signature is generated w.r.t. a statement Y whose witness y is secretly shared among the oracles. When an oracle testifies for an event, it reveals its share of the witness y . We can see that it is natural for oracle-based payments to create multiple pre-signatures on the same message: If Alice wants to pay Bob 5 coins when it rains *or* when it snows, she creates a transaction for 5 coins and encrypts it once for rain and once for snow.

As we have already described, witness extractability only provides security guarantees if an adversary learns exactly one pre-signature on a challenge message m^* , since this correctly models the payment channels. Therefore, we can build an adaptor signature scheme in which any pair of pre-signatures on the same message reveals a full signature, even if the pre-signatures are not adapted. Such an adaptor signature scheme remains witness extractable (according to the definition from [3]) since the adversary, who still only learns one pre-signature on the challenge message, cannot obtain the additional valid signature on the challenge message. However, such an adaptor signature scheme defeats one-wayness, which is the most important security property of oracle-based payments: One-wayness guarantees that an encrypted payment for a threshold of t oracles (a pre-signature on a message m) can only be redeemed (learn a signature on m) if a malicious user provides the testimony of at least t oracles. Leaky pre-signatures break one-wayness since a malicious Bob asks Alice for two encrypted payments on the same transaction message m and learns a valid signature on m from this pair. Thus, Bob can spend transaction m without any testimony.

Stronger Definitions. Each of our counterexamples (c.f. Section 3) shows that the mentioned gaps in the original definitions of adaptor signatures are not theoretical but lead to security flaws in the broad applications of adaptor signatures. Thus, we try to find sufficiently strong definitions of adaptor signatures. The work of Dai *et al.* [14] provides an important contribution to the security of adaptor signatures, as they model security without an implicit application of the primitive to payment channels. They also provide a separating counterexample between the new and the old definitions. However, the counter-example does not break the security of any published application that uses adaptor signatures. Therefore, it is unclear whether the new definitions are only theoretically stronger or if they indeed fix the gaps in the current adaptor security definitions. In contrast, we show that the gaps between the old and the new definitions are indeed practical, as all our explicit attacks are based on counter-examples that are secure w.r.t. the old definitions but insecure w.r.t. the new ones. The definitions of Dai *et al.* include *extractability*, *unique extractability*, and *unlinkability*. These definitions almost cover the applications for adaptor signatures, but we observe in Section 3.2, that there is one important definition missing, which we formalize as *pre-verify soundness*. Looking ahead, we will show in Section 4 that the three definitions of Dai *et al.* alongside pre-verify soundness are sufficient for current adaptor signature applications and we will stick to them: For example, if an adaptor signature scheme is *extractable*, then there are no leaky pre-signatures for that adaptor signature scheme. This is because extractability allows an adversary to see multiple pre-signatures on the challenge message and thus allows an adversary to extract the additional provided information. We re-cite the stronger definitions and show how each counterexample is insecure w.r.t. the stronger security definitions in Section 4.

A Perspective. Dai *et al.* [14] presented a contrived counter-example scheme to substantiate the strength of their definition without explicitly showing the in-

sufficiency of these definitions w.r.t. practical applications. Moreover, the cryptographic community continued using Aumayr et al. definitions even after the work of Dai et al. was public, as evidenced by these publications of [21, 29]. In contrast, through our attacks, we provide a concrete, practical motivation to deviate from prior definitions. Given the rapidly growing interest in adaptors and the financial capital staked on their security, we believe it is prudent to raise awareness about this mismatch in a timely manner.

2.3 A Framework for Constructing Adaptor Signatures

We now focus on our second main contribution, which is a new framework for constructing adaptor signatures. Currently, adaptor signatures are only known for ID-based signature schemes. Two significant challenges with ID-based adaptors are: (a) their security was proven under the definitions in [3] which, as demonstrated earlier, are insufficient beyond payment channels, (b) the only known approach to proving the security of ID-based signatures requires idealized models like the random oracle model. More concerningly, these security proofs use the “full” power of the random oracle model (i.e., programmability), and this is also inherited by the security proofs of the corresponding adaptor signatures. Whether the reliance on (the full power of) idealized models is necessary for proving security is a well-motivated fundamental question throughout cryptography. While the class of ID-based signatures is widely used in cryptocurrencies, there are several non-ID-based signature schemes like BBS+, Waters, and CL that boast desirable properties. Enabling adaptor signatures for them is interesting from both theoretical and practical perspectives.

Dichotomic Signatures. Towards providing a general framework that can capture several algebraic signature schemes, we identify three natural algebraic properties of signature schemes. We refer to the class of signatures as *dichotomic signatures*. These properties will allow us to build adaptor signatures for these signature schemes. A dichotomic signature scheme is a randomized signature scheme Σ equipped with an injective one-way function $\text{OWF} : \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{R'}$, where \mathcal{D}_R and $\mathcal{D}_{R'}$ are randomness spaces mapping Σ 's randomness such that the following properties are satisfied:

- *Decomposability:* there exists efficiently computable randomized algorithms Σ_1, Σ_2 such that for every signing key sk , message m , and randomness r , the signature $\sigma = \Sigma.\text{Sign}(\text{sk}, m; r)$ decomposes into a tuple (σ_1, σ_2) where σ_1 (resp., σ_2) uses $\text{OWF}(r)$ (resp., r) as the random tape. That is,

$$\sigma_1 = \Sigma_1(\text{sk}, m; \text{OWF}(r)); \sigma_2 = \Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m; r) .$$

- *Homomorphism:* Σ_2 admits an additive homomorphism w.r.t. its randomness component. That is, for every signing key sk , message m and randomness $r, y \in \mathcal{D}_R$,

$$\Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m; r + y) = \Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m; r) + y .$$

- *Verifiability*: a signature (σ_1, σ_2) can be verified by just checking an efficient relation between σ_1 and $\text{OWF}(\sigma_2)$. This is captured by the existence of an efficient algorithm Vrfy' that satisfies

$$\text{Vrfy}(\text{vk}, m, (\sigma_1, \sigma_2)) = \text{Vrfy}'(\text{vk}, m, \sigma_1, \text{OWF}(\sigma_2)) ,$$

for the verification algorithm Vrfy of the underlying signature scheme, every verification key vk , and all messages m .

These properties are natural for algebraic signature schemes, and in fact, the abstraction of dichotomic signatures is quite expressive: In Section 5 we show several known schemes relying on different algebraic structures are dichotomic. Examples include the prime-order group based Schnorr signatures [30], the pairing-based Boneh-Boyen-Shacham (BBS+) [7], the RSA-based Camenisch-Lysyanskaya (CL) [12], the class of partitioned signatures [8], and the CDH-based strongly unforgeable Waters signature scheme (Waters+) [8].

Adaptor Signatures for Dichotomic Signatures. Next, we discuss how the abstraction of dichotomic signatures lends itself to a construction of adaptor signature for it w.r.t. the hard relation $\text{Rel} = \{(Y, y) : Y = \text{OWF}(y)\}$. For simplicity, we omit the values sk and m from the function descriptions and describe only the random values used.

- To pre-sign, a message m w.r.t. a statement Y , and a signing key sk , we compute Σ_2 using randomness r but compute Σ_1 using a combined randomness $\text{OWF}(r) \cdot Y$. That is, a pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma} = (\tilde{\sigma}_1, \tilde{\sigma}_2)$ has the form

$$\tilde{\sigma}_1 = \Sigma_1(\text{OWF}(r) \cdot Y); \tilde{\sigma}_2 = \Sigma_2(r).$$

- To adapt a pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma} := (\tilde{\sigma}_1, \tilde{\sigma}_2)$ with witness y , we compute $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$, where $\sigma_1 = \tilde{\sigma}_1$, and $\sigma_2 = \tilde{\sigma}_2 + y$. Note that by the homomorphism property of Σ_2 , σ is a valid signature on m under the randomness $r + y$.
- To extract from a pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma} = (\tilde{\sigma}_1, \tilde{\sigma}_2)$ and a corresponding adapted signature $\sigma = (\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$, we compute $\sigma_2 - \tilde{\sigma}_2 = y$. The correctness of y follows since $\tilde{\sigma}$ was adapted using a valid witness y by computing $\sigma_2 = \tilde{\sigma}_2 + y$.
- For convenience's sake, we omit the pre-verification process and direct the reader to Construction 1 for a more elaborate discussion.

We refer to these adaptor signatures as *dichotomic adaptor* signatures. We now proceed to discuss the security proof.

Proving Security. Ideally, to prove the unforgeability security of adaptor signatures, we would like to reduce it to the unforgeability of the underlying dichotomic signature scheme. Any such reduction would need to simulate the signing as well as the pre-signing oracle for an adaptor signature adversary, *while only having access to the signing oracle in the unforgeability game of the dichotomic signature scheme*. However, it is not clear whether such a task is feasible. To

elaborate, consider the following natural strategy to simulate the pre-signing oracle that takes as input a private key sk and an adversarially chosen message m and statement Y . To compute a pre-signature on this pair, the reduction may query its signing oracle to learn a signature σ on m . Note that this signature σ is a tuple (σ_1, σ_2) where $\sigma_1 = \Sigma_1(\text{OWF}(r))$, and $\sigma_2 = \Sigma_2(r)$ (we again omit the values sk , and m). For this tuple, r is the random coins chosen by the signing oracle, which is kept secret from the reduction. If the reduction had access to the witness y for Y , then it can easily massage σ to a valid pre-signature by computing $\tilde{\sigma} := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2 - y)$. However, since Y is adversarially chosen and from a hard relation, it seems unlikely that the reduction knows the witness. In other words, it seems that the reduction must break the hard relation in order to simulate the pre-sign oracle.

To overcome this challenge, the most common approach adopted in known security proofs for adaptor signature schemes is to rely on the programmability of the random oracle, which we want to avoid. Another approach is to modify the hard relation to now contain the tuple (Y, π) as the statement where π is a NIZK proof-of-knowledge that certifies knowledge of the witness y . Then, the reduction can extract the witness y using the proof-of-knowledge extractor. However, NIZK proof-of-knowledge themselves either require a random oracle model [20] or a trusted-setup [5], which should be avoided in a decentralized setting like ours.

Transparent Reductions. Our key idea to overcome this challenge without relying on idealized models is to open up the reduction that bases the unforgeability of the underlying dichotomic signature scheme to some (possibly interactive) hardness assumption; henceforth called the *unforgeability reduction*. We observe that if the unforgeability reduction satisfies certain structural properties, then we can use its code in a non-black-box way to devise a reduction that bases the security of the adaptor signatures directly on the hardness assumption. Towards this, we introduce the notion of *transparent reductions*⁴ which essentially capture the properties required from the unforgeability reductions.

More specifically, transparent reductions disclose three different algorithms as shown in Fig. 1. A *simulated key-generation* algorithm, a *simulated signing*, and a *break* algorithm that performs the functions as the names suggest: simulate key generation, simulate the signing oracle, and compute the solution for the hard problem, respectively. The adversary $\mathcal{A}_{\text{sign}}$ that breaks the unforgeability of the signature scheme receives as input the public output of the simulated key-generation algorithm and has access to the simulated signing algorithm as an oracle. When $\mathcal{A}_{\text{sign}}$ eventually outputs a valid forgery for the unforgeability game, the break algorithm is used to convert this forgery into a solution for the instance of the hard problem.

For the first step of our proof strategy, we reuse the code of these interfaces in a non-black-box way to provide a signing, key-generation, and break algorithm to

⁴ We call these reductions transparent since we can “see-through” the reduction and use its code in a non-black-box way.

the adversary \mathcal{A}_{AS} of the security of the adaptor signature scheme. In the second

Fig. 1: Visualization of a transparent reduction that reduces unforgeability to a non-interactive hard problem. The instance is a random instance of the non-interactive hard problem.

step, we have to simulate pre-signatures for \mathcal{A}_{AS} , which we do using a property of transparent reductions we call *simulatability*. Simulatability guarantees that having as input the simulated signing key simsk , a message m , and a statement Y , the transparent reduction can compute a simulated pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma}$ that looks indistinguishable from an honestly computed pre-signature. Since computing a signature and massaging it to a pre-signature does not seem feasible as outlined above, the reduction can use the power of the simulated signing key to *directly* compute a simulated pre-signature w.r.t. m and Y . With this direct computation, the reduction does not need to break either the hardness of the relation or the unforgeability of the signature scheme.

Using the power of simulatable transparent reductions, a challenger can provide all needed oracles to an adversary *without* relying on the random oracle model. We show in Section 7, that these simulated oracles lead to a security reduction that breaks the hardness of an underlying hard problem whenever an adversary wins the extractability experiment. This security reduction allows us to obtain the first adaptor signatures in the standard model, which are based on dichotomic adaptor signatures in the standard model. Besides from finding adaptor signatures in the standard model, transparent reductions allow us to prove the security for adaptor signature schemes based on a variety of assumptions using a single construction: We find dichotomic adaptor signatures based on strong RSA, pairings, CDH, and many more (c.f. Section 7).

We believe that transparent reductions are meaningful apart from proving the security of dichotomic adaptor signature schemes due to the following two reasons. First, whenever a primitive adds functionality to a signature scheme (e.g., verifiable encryption of signatures (VES)), it is not a priori clear whether the security of the new primitive can be reduced to the unforgeability of the signature scheme. In such a case, transparent reductions can bootstrap the proving process by removing redundancy: Instead of reducing the hardness of the primitive to the underlying problem, which requires simulating keys, a signing oracle, and providing a break algorithm, using a transparent reduction leverages the algorithms of the already existing reduction from the unforgeability of the signature scheme to the hard problem. Second, transparent reductions for signature schemes open a much broader field for transparent reductions for arbitrary cryptographic primitives, like encryption schemes or message authentication codes. Considering these possible applications, we believe that transparent reductions have future use for any scenario in which a non-black-box reduction removes redundancy from proofs.

Although our proof technique that relies on the new notion of transparent reductions is undoubtedly complex, it streamlines the verification process for subsequent constructions. That is, we need to check if only a few properties hold for the signature schemes' security reduction instead of reducing the security of the final adaptor construction to the underlying hard problem from scratch. Our work has done the bulk of the proof work. What is left to find secure adaptor signatures for a given signature scheme Σ is checking if the signature scheme is dichotomic and if there exists a simulatable transparent reduction from the unforgeability of Σ to the hardness of an underlying hard problem. In practice, many algebraic signature schemes are dichotomic and have a simulatable transparent reduction, as we show in Section 7.

2.4 New Instantiations of Secure Adaptor Signatures

All currently known adaptor signatures rely on the power of the random oracle model to achieve security. Furthermore, the only known security proof holds w.r.t. the security model provided by Aumayr *et al.* [3], that turns out to be insufficient for the novel applications as we show in Section 3. And beyond ID-based signature schemes, it is not clear whether we can generically find adaptor signatures for a given signature scheme. We address these issues by providing a general framework for building adaptor signatures that leads to secure instances w.r.t. our definitions in the standard model.

Adaptor signatures in the standard model are desirable since the goal of modern cryptography is to use as few and as weak assumptions as possible. Furthermore, many standardized signatures that are used in a wide variety of applications are in the standard model. A famous example is the Boneh-Boyen-Shacham (BBS+) signature scheme [7]. The BBS+ signature scheme is the basis for anonymous credentials (AC) and several other privacy-preserving protocols [9, 10, 2, 32], and is also standardized and deployed in many real-world systems [23, 22,

19]. Our work shows how to build adaptor signatures for BBS+, thereby connecting the fairness properties of adaptor signatures with the privacy-preserving properties of BBS+.

Besides BBS+, we also show how to find adaptor signatures for many existent strongly unforgeable signature schemes Σ with two easy checks: First, one has to check if Σ is dichotomic, and second, if the security reduction \mathcal{R} from the SUF-CMA security of Σ to an underlying hard problem is transparent and simulatable. We identify that the signature schemes Camenisch-Lysyanskaya (CL) [12], the class of partitioned signatures [8], and the strongly unforgeable Waters signature (Waters+) [8] are all dichotomic and have simulatable transparent reductions. Hence, we can build adaptor signatures for these signature schemes and find the first three secure adaptor signatures in the standard model. The security of these adaptor signatures is based on well-known (mild) assumptions, such as the CDH assumption or the strong RSA assumption, rather than the programmability of a heuristic model.

Furthermore, we show that all existent ID-based adaptor signature schemes also align with our framework. Since our framework works generically, we do not have to prove the security of each of our new instantiations separately. This means that the strong security definitions for adaptor signatures, as discussed in Section 4, carry over to any dichotomic signature scheme with a simulatable transparent reduction. Since ID-based signatures are dichotomic and have a simulatable transparent reduction, our framework also implies the security of Schnorr adaptor signatures w.r.t. to the stronger security definitions of Dai *et al.*. This renders the current implementations for protocols based on Schnorr adaptor signatures secure.

3 Security Gaps in Adaptor Signature Applications

This section shows three shortcomings in the current formalization of adaptor signatures. We provide simple counterexamples of adaptor signatures that are secure in the definitions of [17, 3] but result in insecure real-world applications. To address each shortcoming, we follow a three-step approach. We first explain the application it affects and its key building blocks. Next, we show how these building blocks are instantiated using adaptor signatures. In the final step, we construct an adaptor signature scheme that trivially breaks the application while being secure w.r.t. the definitions of [17, 3].

We wish to emphasize that the security gaps we identify do not affect the security of the concrete constructions used in these applications. Instead, we aim to highlight gaps in the definitions of adaptor signatures that potentially lead to *bad* instantiations, affecting the application’s overall security.

3.1 Breaking VweTS Using Signature Leaky Pre-Signatures

Madathil et al. [24] introduced *verifiable witness encryption based on threshold signatures (VweTS)* at NDSS’23 that with applications in oracle-based condi-

tional payments for blockchains. Their instantiation of VweTS uses adaptor signatures as one of the many building blocks. In this section, we present another gap in the definitions of adaptor signatures that leads to an attack against their instantiation of VweTS. In the following, we first recall relevant parts of their construction necessary to follow our attack. We then construct the adaptor signature scheme that satisfies the security definitions but leads to a devastating attack when used as a building block in the construction of VweTS.

Verifiable Witness Encryption Based on Threshold Signatures (VweTS). A VweTS scheme uses two signature schemes, namely, $\Sigma := (\text{KGen}, \text{Sign}, \text{Vf})$ and $\Sigma' := (\text{KGen}', \text{Sign}', \text{Vf}')$ and provides the efficient algorithms $(\text{EncSig}, \text{VfEnc}, \text{DecSig})$. We refer to Σ' as the signature scheme and Σ as the transaction signature scheme. A VweTS protocol is run between an encryptor that encrypts transaction signatures on transaction messages into ciphertexts and a decryptor that decrypts these ciphertexts to obtain transaction signatures. The important part is that the decryption is not done using a decryption key but rather using a sufficient number of instance signatures on instance messages. An instance signature confirms the instance message by a third party identified by an instance verification key vk' . We call these third parties instance signers from now on.

To understand our attack, it is sufficient to focus on the protocols EncSig , and DecSig and we refer to [24] for a more formal description of VweTS.

- The signature encryption algorithm EncSig encrypts a tuple of signatures $(\sigma_j)_{j \in [M]}$ on transaction messages $(m_j)_{j \in [M]}$ to produce a ciphertext c . The ciphertext c is generated with respect to a tuple of instance verification keys $(\text{vk}'_i)_{i \in [N]}$, and instance messages $(m'_j)_{j \in [M]}$ as well.
- The decryption algorithm DecSig takes as input a tuple of ρ (valid) instance signatures σ'_i (under the instance verification keys vk'_i) on an instance message m'_j . It returns the transaction signature σ_j on the transaction message m_j .

The main security property of a VweTS scheme is called one-wayness, which intuitively guarantees that no adversary can output a valid transaction signature forgery σ^* for a transaction message m_j encrypted in a VweTS ciphertext c without access to at least ρ number of valid instance signatures on the corresponding instance messages m'_j . To formalize one-wayness, an adversary \mathcal{A} can corrupt up to $\rho - 1$ instance signers and has access to a signature encryption oracle that runs EncSig on adversarially chosen instance messages and transaction messages. We omit the other oracles, as our attack will not use them. Furthermore, our attack only queries the signature encryption oracle once. Eventually, \mathcal{A} has to output a signature forgery σ^* , an index j^* that marks the j^* -th transaction message in its encryption oracle call. Since our attack only queries the signature encryption oracle once, \mathcal{A} 's output has to satisfy the following conditions to win the one-wayness experiment:

1. The adversary corrupted less than ρ instance signers;
2. the signature σ^* verifies under the challengers verification key vk and the j^* -th transaction message m_{j^*} .

VweTS Instantiation Using Adaptor Signatures. Madathil *et al.* also presented VweTS constructions, which utilize adaptor signatures as a building block. Intuitively, the encryption of a transaction signature on a transaction message m_j consists of an adaptor pre-signature on m_j with respect to a random statement $Y_j := g^{y_j}$ for $y_j \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p^*$. The witness y_j is verifiably secret-shared, and each share is encrypted using a special encryption scheme that is irrelevant to our context. The only information about this special encryption scheme we need to know here is that the j -th ciphertext can be decrypted given ρ instance signatures on the instance message m'_j . To decrypt a signature on the message m_j , one has to *adapt* the pre-signature on m_j to a valid signature using the witness y_j . Recall that the witness y_j is available by decrypting ρ number of the special ciphertexts given the instance signatures.

Madathil *et al.* proposed the security of the VweTS construction utilizing the security of the used adaptor signature scheme in a theorem, which we reiterate below as Proposition 1.

Proposition 1 (Theorem 1 from [24], informal). *Let Σ and Σ' be secure signature schemes, WES be secure witness encryption based on signatures, AS be a secure adaptor signature scheme for Σ and the relation Rel. Let $\Pi := (\text{Setup}, \text{Prove}, \text{Vrfy})$ be a NIZK proof system satisfying simulation soundness. Then, the VweTS construction from [24] achieves one-wayness.*

Breaking VweTS from Adaptor Signatures. Contrary to this proposition, we claim that there exists an adaptor signature scheme AS that is secure in accordance with the former definitions, but if the VweTS construction from [24] is instantiated with AS, one-wayness does not hold. We prove our claim in two steps. First, we construct a secure adaptor signature scheme AS, in which multiple pre-signatures on the same message can reveal information on an additional valid signature on the same message. Second, we show how an adversary wins the game ExpOWay with overwhelming probability if a VweTS is instantiated using AS'.

Theorem 1. *Let Σ, Σ', Π , and WES be as in Proposition 1. There exists a secure adaptor signature scheme AS' for the signature scheme Σ and the relation Rel, such that the VweTS construction from [24] instantiated with AS' does not achieve one-wayness.*

An Adaptor Signature with Leaky Pre-Signatures. In both the witness extractability and aEUF-CMA security definitions, the adversary \mathcal{A} of the adaptor signature is allowed to query the pre-signing oracle on a challenge message m^* exactly one time. However, in the VweTS security game, the adversary \mathcal{A} can query the EncSig oracle with a tuple of transaction messages (m_0, \dots, m_M) . Thereby, \mathcal{A} can learn at least two pre-signatures on the same message with different random adaptor statements for each.

Our counter-example is inspired by [14]. Dai *et al.* propose a counter-example that shows a gap if an adversary can see two pre-signatures on the same message

and the same statement. This counterexample can not break Proposition 1, since the VweTS construction samples a random statement for each pre-signature, and the probability of learning two pre-signatures on the same message is negligible. Furthermore, they use a pseudorandom function instead of a random function. As a key for the PRF, they also use the signing key sk . Since PRFs are not leakage-resilient in general, it can be detectable by an adversary if it learns $\tilde{\sigma}, \text{PRF}(\text{sk}, m, Y)$, or $\tilde{\sigma}, r$ for a random value $r \leftarrow_{\$} \{0, 1\}^\ell$ (c.f. game hop between \mathcal{G}_0 and \mathcal{G}_1 in [14], proof of their Theorem 3). Therefore, we do not assume their counterexample to be proven secure but follow the flavor of this counterexample in a provable manner.

To overcome the described issues, our counter-example uses hash functions modeled as random oracles instead of pseudorandom functions. Using the RO is reasonable since the VweTS constructions in [24] are based on Schnorr and ECDSA signatures that already utilize the random oracle model for security. On a high level, our counter-example adaptor signature scheme AS' pre-signs a message-statement pair (m, Y) using the underlying pre-sign algorithm of AS and by appending a random element r to this pre-signature. Depending on a coin toss, the random element is either $\mathcal{H}(\text{sk}, m)$, i.e., the output of the random oracle on the input of the signing key sk and the message m or the XOR of $\mathcal{H}(\text{sk}, m)$ and a valid signature on m . AS' is formally defined in Figure 2.

$\text{pSign}'(\text{sk}, m, Y)$	$\text{pVrfy}'(\text{vk}, m, Y, \tilde{\sigma})$
1 : $\tilde{\sigma} \leftarrow \text{pSign}(\text{sk}, m, Y)$	1 : $(\tilde{\sigma}', \perp) := \tilde{\sigma}$
2 : $b \leftarrow_{\$} \{0, 1\}$	2 : return $\text{pVrfy}(\text{vk}, m, Y, \tilde{\sigma}')$
3 : $r_0 \leftarrow \mathcal{H}(\text{sk}, m)$	$\text{Extract}'(\text{vk}, \tilde{\sigma}, \sigma, Y)$
4 : $\sigma \leftarrow \text{Sign}(\text{sk}, m)$	1 : $(\tilde{\sigma}', \perp) := \tilde{\sigma}$
5 : $r_1 := r_0 \oplus \sigma$	2 : return $\text{Extract}(\text{vk}, \tilde{\sigma}', \sigma, Y)$
6 : return $(\tilde{\sigma}, r_b)$	$\text{Adapt}'(\text{vk}, \tilde{\sigma}, y)$
	1 : $(\tilde{\sigma}', \perp) := \tilde{\sigma}$
	2 : return $\text{Adapt}(\text{vk}, \tilde{\sigma}', y)$

Fig. 2: A secure adaptor signature scheme AS' , for which two pre-signatures on the same message can leak an additional signature. We show the security of this adaptor signature scheme in the full version.

How an Adversary Can Break the One-Wayness of VweTS We now show how an adversary \mathcal{A} can break the one-wayness of VweTS if the construction in [24] is instantiated using AS' . One way for an adversary \mathcal{A} to win the game ExpOWay is to compute a verifying signature on a challenge message m_j by only querying the EncSig oracle and not querying the signature and the instance

signature oracles related to m_j . Let us assume for simplicity that $M = 2$, where M is the size of the message tuples used in `EncSig`. Keeping this in mind, the adversary queries the oracle `EncSigO` on random instance messages m'_0, m'_1 , and on a tuple of transaction messages (m_0, m_0) . Internally, the oracle computes two pre-signatures on the message m_0 with random statements and outputs the pre-signatures as part of the `VweTS` ciphertext c . Therefore, with probability $1/2$, the adversary can learn a valid signature on the message m_0 by XOR-ing the two random elements from the two pre-signatures returned by the oracle. In the generic case of M being some arbitrary polynomial in the security parameter, the adversary can use the above strategy and win with overwhelming probability $1 - (1/2)^{M-1}$. This breaks the one-wayness of adaptor signature-based `VweTS` constructions.

3.2 Breaking Blind Hubs Using Unadaptable Adaptor Signatures

The second definitional gap stems from the fact that the security definitions do not hold for statements, not in the language of the relation `Rel`, i.e., $Y \notin \mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}}$. This gap is not a problem for early applications, such as payment channels, because the user computing the statement also adapts the corresponding pre-signature. However, we show that this gap leads to devastating attacks in recent applications, such as coin-mixing, which allows the adversary to steal coins.

In the following, we first give a counterexample in which a valid pre-signature for a non-language statement cannot be adapted to a valid signature. Then, we show that this leads to an immediate loss of fairness in coin-mixing applications [29, 21].

Flexible Blind Conditional Signatures. Qin *et al.* [29] propose the new notion of flexible blind conditional signatures (FBCS). FBCS are blind conditional signatures in which the hub `H` (cf. Section 3.3) only learns a commitment on a transaction rather than the transaction in plaintext. Similar to the security notions of ordinary BCS, a crucial security requirement for FBCS is *unlockability*. Unlockability guarantees that no malicious hub `H` can refrain coins by running a `PPromise` and a related `PSolve`. In the unlockability security experiment, an adversary \mathcal{A} can run a single execution of `PPromise` and a related `PSolve`. \mathcal{A} wins the experiment if he:

- Outputs a valid signature on a transaction message from `Bob` to \mathcal{A} ;
- the puzzle open algorithm run by `Bob` does not reveal a valid signature from \mathcal{A} to `Bob`.

FBCS Instantiation Using Adaptor Signatures. Qin *et al.* provide a construction for a FBCS based on the `DLog` relation and the ECDSA signature scheme, which also uses adaptor signature schemes for ECDSA. Due to the similarity of the FBCS construction and the BCS construction, we refer the reader to Section 3.3 for a discussion of this construction. The authors refer to this FBCS construction as `BlindHub` and formally claim its security:

Proposition 2 (Theorem 1 from [29], informal). *Let Π_{Enc} be a linear-homomorphic encryption scheme, Π_{AS} a secure adaptor signature scheme, Π_{BAS} a secure BAS scheme, Π_{RSORC} a secure signature on randomizable commitments scheme, Π_{NIZK} a sound proof system. If the one-more DLog assumption is assumed to be hard, then the BlindHub protocol is a secure, flexible blind conditional signature scheme.*

Breaking (Flexible) Blind Conditional Signatures from Adaptor Signatures. Contrary to this proposition, we claim that the BlindHub construction is insecure in general if it is instantiated using an unadaptable adaptor signature scheme.

Theorem 2. *If the BlindHub protocol of [29] is instantiated with a unadaptable adaptor signature scheme AS' and a relation that has malicious statements for valid witnesses, then it is in general not a secure flexible blind conditional signature scheme.*

We prove Theorem 2 in two steps: First, we show how to build unadaptable adaptor signatures. Second, we show how to break unlockability using unadaptable adaptor signatures.

Construction of an Unadaptable Adaptor Signature Scheme. Let AS be a secure adaptor signature for some signature scheme Σ and the relation Rel , such that the language \mathcal{L}_{Rel} is efficiently decidable: there exists an efficient algorithm that outputs 1 if $Y \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}}$, and 0 otherwise. Given AS , we construct a new adaptor signature AS' , that adheres to the same security properties of AS , and therefore also to the adaptability notion, but which trivially leads to an attack for statements not in the language of the relation Rel , i.e., $Y \notin \mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}}$. We model this malicious functionality by letting the pre-signing algorithm output \perp for statements not in the language of the relation. The pre-verification algorithm accepts \perp as a valid pre-signature if $Y \notin \mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}}$.

Therefore, \perp is a valid pre-signature on a malicious statement, and thus Adapt can not adapt \perp to a valid signature on the inputs of a public key vk and a valid witness y . We provide both a formal description of AS' and security proofs w.r.t. the former definitions in the full version of this work.

Breaking Unlockability. In a coin mixing setup, an adversary acting as hub H can break unlockability if the used adaptor signature scheme is unadaptable for dishonest statements: In the puzzle promise phase, the hub H samples a malicious statement Y' and computes a valid pre-signature on Y' by simply outputting \perp . The other party Bob accepts the puzzle since the pre-signature \perp pre-verifies. Bob now runs the puzzle solve protocol together with H . When the puzzle is solved, H learns a signature and is paid by Bob . However, Bob can not adapt the pre-signature (i.e., \perp) provided by H even if he learns a valid witness for the statement Y' , so Bob can not claim a payment by H . The *concrete instantiations* provided in [21, 29] avoid this kind of attack since the relation has only witnesses for statements that are well-formed, and H must prove the knowledge of a witness

using a NIZK. Yet, Proposition 2 does not hold in general: If we instantiate the protocols with a relation, where maliciously chosen statements $Y \notin \mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}}$ can have valid witnesses, the hub H can prove knowledge of the witness while pre-signing w.r.t. a malicious statement. The language $\mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}} := \{((1, Y), y) \mid Y = g^y; y \in \mathbb{Z}_p\}$ yields such a hard relation. When instantiated with such a hard relation, the blind hub protocol is insecure since H can prove the knowledge of a witness for a maliciously computed statement of the form $(0, Y)$. This statement is clearly not in the language since the first bit is a 0.

3.3 Breaking Coin-Mixing Using Malleable Pre-Signatures

Glaeser et al. presented a protocol for coin-mixing at CCS'22 that utilizes blind conditional signatures (BCS) as a foundational component [21]. The authors demonstrate the instantiation of BCS with adaptor signatures. However, we show through a counter-example that a black-box construction of BCS from any adaptor signature scheme is not possible in general. For this, we give our counter-example that satisfies current adaptor signature definitions but yields an insecure BCS scheme, thus compromising the security of the coin-mixing protocol A^2L^+ as formulated in [21]. In fact, the cryptographic primitives used in the recent work of Qin et al. [29] also suffers from the same drawback. But for simplicity, we will be using [21] to demonstrate the security gap. The crux of our attack is the exploitation of pre-signature malleability. A malleable pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma}$ on a public key vk , message m , and statement Y can be converted into a distinct pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma}'$ that verifies on the same public key, message, and statement, but adapts to a signature different from the one that we would get from adapting $\tilde{\sigma}$. Obtaining two different valid signatures from a single pre-signature breaks fairness for coin mixing, as we elaborate in our contract attack against the protocol from Glaeser *et al.* in the full version of this work.

4 Correct Security Definitions for Adaptor Signatures

The attacks presented in Section 3 serve as clear indications that the security properties captured in the definition of adaptor signatures in [17, 3] are insufficient for most applications. To address this issue, we identify a new security property for adaptor signatures called *pre-verify soundness*, which is important for certain applications such as coin mixing [21, 29] and Oracle-based payments [25]. Furthermore, we advise the use of *extractability*, *unique extractability*, and *unlinkability*, which were provided by Dai *et al.*

4.1 Definitions of Dai et al.

The work of Dai, Okamoto, and Yamamoto [14] takes a significant step towards finding the right security definitions for adaptor signatures by proposing stronger security properties that a good adaptor signature scheme should satisfy (over the properties captured by [17, 3]). These properties are *extractability*, *unique*

extractability, and *unlinkability*. We streamline these security definitions and defer a formal definition to the full version of this work.

4.2 Pre-Verify Soundness

We propose *pre-verify soundness* as a new security property for adaptors. Informally, it ensures that the pre-verification algorithm satisfies *computational* soundness w.r.t. the relation Rel . In particular, pVrfy should reject pre-signatures computed using statements $Y \notin \text{Rel}$. Intuitively, pre-verify soundness ensures that every valid pre-signature can be adapted to a full signature, and one can extract a witness from it. This complements the property of pre-signature adaptability, which is restricted to honestly generated pre-signatures on statements in the relation. Pre-verify soundness is important for applications in which the pre-signer also computes the statement w.r.t., which the pre-signature is computed on, since without pre-verify soundness, a malicious signer can trick a verifier into accepting pre-signatures which cannot be adapted even in the presence of a valid witness (c.f. Section 3.2). If the application guarantees that the verifying party always computes the statement, pre-verify soundness might not be required from the underlying adaptor signature scheme, and more efficient solutions can be used.

Definition 1 (Computational Pre-Verify Soundness). *An adaptor signature scheme AS satisfies computational pre-verify soundness if for every PPT adversary \mathcal{A} there exists a negligible function ν such that for every $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$ and polynomially-bounded $Y \notin \mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}}$,*

$$\Pr[(\text{sk}, \text{vk}) \leftarrow \text{KGen}(\lambda), (m, \tilde{\sigma}) \leftarrow \mathcal{A}(\text{sk}) : \text{pVrfy}(\text{vk}, m, \tilde{\sigma}, Y) = 1] \leq \nu(\lambda) .$$

For applications where the adversary is allowed to also choose their signing and verification keys, the following stronger statistical notion of pre-verify soundness is useful. The stronger notion is fundamentally similar to the notion of non-interactive proofs in the plain model. Like non-interactive plain model proofs, the statistical notion of pre-verify soundness is unachievable for *non-trivial* NP relations. For NP relations where checking membership can be done efficiently (e.g., discrete-log language over efficiently recognizable groups), statistically pre-verify soundness can be achieved simply by letting pVrfy algorithm decide membership of the given statement. Nevertheless, we explicitly define this as an additional property for pVrfy as prior constructions of adaptor signatures nor the application they were used in did this check, resulting in a break of the application as discussed in Section 3.

Definition 2 (Statistical Pre-Verify Soundness). *An adaptor signature scheme AS satisfies statistical pre-verify soundness if for every $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, polynomially-bounded $Y \notin \mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}}$, key pair (sk, vk) in the support of $\text{KGen}(\lambda)$,*

$$\Pr[\exists(m, \tilde{\sigma}) : \text{pVrfy}(\text{vk}, m, Y) = 1] = 0 .$$

Pre-Verify Soundness Prevents Non-Adaptable Adaptor Signatures. Our counter-example in Section 3.2 does not achieve pre-verify soundness, since \perp is a valid pre-signature for a statement that is not in the language of the hard relation.

5 Dichotomic Signature Schemes

In this section, we propose dichotomic signatures, which serve as a suitable abstraction of signature schemes for our framework. Furthermore, we show how dichotomic signatures can be transformed into dichotomic adaptor signature schemes *without* changing the verification algorithm.

Definition 3 (Dichotomic Signature Scheme). *Let $\text{OWF} : \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{R'}$ be a homomorphic function. A signature scheme $\Sigma = (\text{KGen}, \text{Sign}, \text{Vrfy})$ with key space \mathcal{D}_K , message-space \mathcal{D}_M , randomness space \mathcal{D}_R , and signature space $\mathcal{D}_{\sigma_1} \times \mathcal{D}_R$ is a dichotomic signature w.r.t. the function OWF if the following holds:*

Decomposability. The signature σ consists of two parts $\sigma = (\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ that can efficiently be computed by the algorithms $\Sigma_1 : \mathcal{D}_K \times \mathcal{D}_M \times \mathcal{D}_{R'} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{\sigma_1}$ and $\Sigma_2 : \mathcal{D}_K \times \mathcal{D}_M \times \mathcal{D}_{\sigma_1} \times \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_R$ such that $\Sigma.\text{Sign}(\text{sk}, m; r) = (\sigma_1, \sigma_2) = (\Sigma_1(\text{sk}, m; \text{OWF}(r)), \Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m, \sigma_1; r))$.

Verifiability. There exists an DPT algorithm $\text{Vrfy}' : \mathcal{D}_K \times \mathcal{D}_M \times \mathcal{D}_{\sigma_1} \times \mathcal{D}_{R'} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that the following holds:

$$\Sigma.\text{Vrfy}(\text{vk}, m, (\sigma_1, \sigma_2)) = \text{Vrfy}'(\text{vk}, m, \sigma_1, \text{OWF}(\sigma_2)) .$$

Homomorphism. The computation of the algorithm Σ_2 is homomorphic in the randomness, that is, for all $y \in \mathcal{D}_R$

$$\Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m, \sigma_1; r) + y = \Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m, \sigma_1; r + y) .$$

Note that we wrote the homomorphisms with arithmetic operators for additive groups \mathcal{D}_R for better readability. The definition holds for groups that have arbitrary arithmetic operations.

Constructing Adaptor Signatures from Dichotomic Signatures. We now construct adaptor signatures from dichotomic signatures in a black-box way. In Section 7, we instantiate this generic construction with BBS^+ . In the full version of this work, we also instantiate CL^+ and Waters^+ signature schemes, yielding the first *natural* adaptor signatures in the standard model.

Construction 1 *Let $\text{OWF} : \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{R'}$ be a homomorphic function. Let $\Sigma = (\text{KGen}, \text{Sign}, \text{Vrfy})$ be a dichotomic signature scheme with respect to the function OWF . Let Rel be the canonical hard relation with auxiliary information for OWF . The adaptor signature scheme $\text{AS} = (\text{pSign}, \text{Adapt}, \text{pVrfy}, \text{Extract})$ is defined in Figure 3.*

We claim the security of Construction 1 in Theorem 3. The formal proof of Theorem 3 requires a novel non-black-box proof technique that we introduce in Section 6. Subsequently, we provide a formal proof of this theorem in Section 7.

$\text{pSign}(\text{sk}, m, Y)$	$\text{Adapt}(\text{vk}, \tilde{\sigma}, y)$
1 : if $\text{AuxVrfy}(\text{sk}, Y, \text{aux}) = 0$ return \perp	1 : $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) := \tilde{\sigma}$
2 : $r \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_R$	2 : $\tilde{\sigma}_2 = \sigma_2 + y$
3 : $\sigma_1 := \Sigma_1(\text{sk}, m; \text{OWF}(r) \cdot Y)$	3 : return $(\sigma_1, \tilde{\sigma}_2)$
4 : $\sigma_2 := \Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m, \sigma_1; r)$	
5 : return (σ_1, σ_2)	
$\text{pVrfy}(\text{vk}, m, Y, \tilde{\sigma})$	$\text{Extract}(\text{vk}, \tilde{\sigma}, \sigma, Y)$
1 : if $\text{StmtVrfy}(\text{vk}, Y, \text{aux}) = 0$ return 0	1 : $(\sigma_1, \sigma'_2) := \tilde{\sigma}$
2 : $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) := \tilde{\sigma}$	2 : $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) := \sigma$
3 : return $\text{Vrfy}'(\text{vk}, m, \sigma_1, \text{OWF}(\sigma_2) \cdot Y)$	3 : return $\sigma_2 - \sigma'_2$

Fig. 3: Dichotomic Adaptor Signature Construction

Theorem 3. *Let $\text{OWF} : \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{R'}$ be an injective homomorphic one-way function, and Rel be a canonical hard relation with auxiliary input for OWF . Let Σ be a dichotomic signature scheme with respect to OWF and let AS be a dichotomic adaptor signature scheme for both Σ and Rel as per Construction 1. If Σ is SUF-CMA secure and has a simulatable transparent reduction \mathcal{T} from the SUF-CMA security of Σ to an underlying hard problem Π , then AS achieves full extractability, unique extractability, and unlinkability. If the membership of the statement in the language \mathcal{L}_{Rel} can be checked efficiently, Construction 1 achieves pre-verify soundness.*

6 Transparent Reductions For Signatures

In this section, we introduce a novel *non-black-box* proof technique to prove the security of dichotomic adaptor signatures (c.f. Construction 1). In the following, we provide a formalization of transparent reductions and show in the next sections that a) the security proofs of many signature schemes have transparent reductions and b) how to make non-black-box use of the transparent reduction in our security proof for adaptor signatures.

Definition 4 (Transparent Reduction). *A transparent reduction $\mathcal{T} = (\text{SimKg}, \text{SimSign}, \text{Break})$ for a (non-interactive) hard problem $\Pi = (I, V)$ with black-box access to an PPT adversary \mathcal{A} consists of the following PPT algorithms: $((\text{simsk}, \text{simpk}), \text{pp}) \leftarrow \text{SimKg}(1^\lambda, \text{inst})$. The input to the simulated key-generation algorithm $\text{SimKg}(\text{inst})$ (resp. $\text{SimKg}^{\mathcal{O}}$) is the security parameter 1^λ , and an instance inst of the hard problem Π . It outputs a key pair $(\text{simpk}, \text{simsk})$, and public parameters pp , where simpk is a simulated public and simsk is a simulated private key.*

$\sigma \leftarrow \text{SimSign}(\text{simsk}, m)$. The signing algorithm SimSign takes as input a simulated signing key simsk and some message m , it outputs a signature σ . We denote by $Q_{\text{SimSign}} = \{(m_1, \sigma_1), \dots, (m_q, \sigma_q)\}$ the set of all query and answer pairs to SimSign and by $Q_{\mathcal{O}} = \{(y_1, x_1), \dots, (y_{q'}, x_{q'})\}$ the query and answer pairs to the oracle \mathcal{O} . The same holds for $\text{SimSign}^{\mathcal{O}}$.

$\text{sol} \leftarrow \text{Break}(\text{simsk}, Q_{\text{SimSign}}, (m^*, \sigma^*), \text{inst})$. The input of the breaking algorithm Break (resp. $\text{Break}^{\mathcal{O}}$) is a simulated private key simsk , the set of query/answer pairs to the sign interface $Q_{\text{SimSign}} = \{(m_1, \sigma_1), \dots, (m_q, \sigma_q)\}$ (and the set $Q_{\mathcal{O}} = \{(y_1, x_1), \dots, (y_{q'}, x_{q'})\}$ of queries to \mathcal{O}), a putative forgery (m^*, σ^*) , and an instance inst of the hard problem Π . It returns a putative solution sol .

Definition 5 (Simulatable Transparent Reductions for Dichotomic Signatures). Let $\Sigma = (\text{KGen}, \text{Sign}, \text{Vrfy})$ be a dichotomic signature scheme based on the function $\text{OWF} : \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{R'}$ and $\mathcal{T} = (\text{SimKg}, \text{SimSign}, \text{Break})$ be a transparent reduction from the SUF-CMA security of Σ to an underlying hard problem Π . We refer to \mathcal{T} as a simulatable transparent reduction for a canonical hard relation of OWF if the following holds: There is an efficient algorithm Sim that on input a simulated secret key $\text{simsk} \leftarrow \text{SimKg}(\text{inst})$, a message $m \in \mathcal{D}_M$ and a image $Y \in \mathcal{D}_{R'}$ of the homomorphic function OWF outputs a value $\tilde{\sigma}$, such that for any PPT distinguisher \mathcal{D} and for each hard instance $\text{inst} \in \Pi$,

$$|\Pr[\text{Exp}_{\mathcal{D}}^1(\text{inst}, 1^\lambda) = 1] - \Pr[\text{Exp}_{\mathcal{D}}^0(\text{inst}, 1^\lambda) = 1]| \leq \nu(\lambda)$$

holds, where Fig. 4 shows the corresponding games.

$\text{Exp}_{\mathcal{D}}^0(1^\lambda)$	$\text{Exp}_{\mathcal{D}}^1(1^\lambda, \text{inst})$
1 : $(\text{sk}, \text{vk}) \leftarrow \Sigma.\text{KGen}(1^\lambda)$	1 : $(\text{simsk}, \text{simpk}) \leftarrow \mathcal{T}.\text{SimKg}(1^\lambda, \text{inst})$
2 : $b' \leftarrow \mathcal{D}^{\mathcal{O}_0(\text{sk}, \cdot)}(\text{vk})$	2 : $b' \leftarrow \mathcal{D}^{\mathcal{O}_1(\text{simsk}, \cdot)}(\text{simpk})$
3 : return $b' == 0$	3 : return $b' == 1$
$\mathcal{O}_0(\text{sk}, m, Y)$	$\mathcal{O}_1(\text{simsk}, m, Y)$
1 : $r \leftarrow \mathcal{D}_R$	1 : return $\text{Sim}(\text{simsk}, m, Y)$
2 : $\sigma_1 := \Sigma_1(\text{sk}, m; \text{OWF}(r) \cdot Y)$	
3 : $\sigma_2 := \Sigma_2(\text{sk}, m, \sigma_1; r)$	
4 : return (σ_1, σ_2)	

Fig. 4: The simulatability game for transparent reductions.

Simulatable transparent reductions provide an additional oracle compared to the oracles used in signature schemes, namely the pre-signature oracle. The adversary having access to this additional oracle raises the question of which signatures are suitable inputs for the transparent reduction's breaking algorithm. To

answer this question, we define *fresh signatures*. Simply put, we consider a signature fresh if it hasn't been obtained by an oracle or using trivial transformations on oracle outputs. We formalize fresh signatures below.

Definition 6 (Fresh Signature). *A signature σ is fresh if it is not output by an oracle. If a pre-signature $\tilde{\sigma} = (\tilde{\sigma}_1, \tilde{\sigma}_2)$ for a statement Y is output by an oracle, we mark each signature $\sigma^* = (\sigma_1^*, \sigma_2^*)$ as non-fresh that satisfies $\sigma_1^* = \tilde{\sigma}_1$ and $\sigma_2^* - \tilde{\sigma}_2 = y'$ such that $\text{OWF}(y') = Y$.*

7 Secure Dichotomic Adaptor Signatures

In this section, we show the security of dichotomic adaptor signatures (c.f. Construction 1) by proving extractability, unique extractability, unlinkability, and pre-verify soundness. Afterward, we show how to build adaptor signatures from BBS^+ . We defer the examples for adaptor signatures from CL^+ and Waters^+ to the full version of this work. In addition, we show in the full version of this work that our framework also covers ID-based signature schemes, which a previous work [3] showed w.r.t. a weaker security model.

Lemma 1 (Extractability). *Let $\text{OWF} : \mathcal{D}_R \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_{R'}$ be an injective homomorphic one-way function, and Rel be a canonical hard relation with auxiliary input for OWF . Let Σ be a dichotomic signature scheme with respect to OWF and let AS be a dichotomic adaptor signature scheme for both Σ and Rel as per Construction 1. If Σ is SUF-CMA secure and has a simulatable transparent reduction \mathcal{T} from the SUF-CMA security of Σ to an underlying hard problem Π , then AS satisfies full extractability.*

Proof. We prove this lemma using the algorithms provided by the simulatable transparent reduction \mathcal{T} given by Σ . We assume towards contradiction that there exists an adversary \mathcal{A} against the full extractability of AS , and we build a reduction \mathcal{R} to break an instance inst of the underlying hard problem of Σ using the transparent reduction \mathcal{T} . The reduction \mathcal{R} has as input the instance inst and simulates the game $\text{Ext}_{\mathcal{A}, \text{AS}}$ to the adversary \mathcal{A} . This simulation is possible, as \mathcal{R} simulates a public key vk and a signing oracle by reusing the code of \mathcal{T} . The pre-signing oracle is simulated by \mathcal{R} using the algorithm Sim provided by \mathcal{T} . When \mathcal{A} outputs a valid forgery, i.e., a message-signature pair (m^*, σ^*) , the reduction \mathcal{R} can use this forgery to break inst using the Break algorithm of the transparent reduction \mathcal{T} . The simulation of Ext provided by \mathcal{R} to \mathcal{A} is indistinguishable from the original Ext game from \mathcal{A} 's point of view due to a series of game hops with a negligible transition. These game hops range from the game \mathcal{G}_0 , which is the original Ext game, to the game \mathcal{G}_3 , in which each valid forgery provided by \mathcal{A} can be used as input to the Break algorithm, such that Break breaks the instance inst .

Game \mathcal{G}_0 : The first game \mathcal{G}_0 is the original Ext game. Since \mathcal{G}_0 simulates the Ext game perfectly, it holds that $\Pr[\text{Ext}(\lambda) = 1] = \Pr[\mathcal{G}_0(\lambda) = 1]$.

Game \mathcal{G}_1 : The second game \mathcal{G}_1 only differs from game \mathcal{G}_0 when it aborts. We call this event $\text{Break}_{\text{Rel}}$. At an intuitive level, $\text{Break}_{\text{Rel}}$ occurs if the forgery of the adversary allows breaking a challenge instance of the hard relation. This game hop does not differ from Ext if the adversary returns an adapted pre-signature on a non-challenge statement since the winning condition covers this already.

Claim. Let $\text{Break}_{\text{Rel}}$ be the event, whereby \mathcal{G}_1 aborts. Then, the adversary \mathcal{A} found a signature forgery σ^* that allows extracting a challenge witness using a previously output pre-signature. If $\text{Break}_{\text{Rel}}$ happens, then we can build a reduction \mathcal{R} that can break the hardness of the hard relation Rel . Thus, $\text{Break}_{\text{Rel}}$ occurs only with negligible probability $\nu_1(1^\lambda)$.

Game \mathcal{G}_2 : In this game, we replace the key generation algorithm, the signing algorithm, and the pre-signing algorithm with the corresponding simulated algorithms provided by the simulatable transparent reduction \mathcal{T} .

Claim. By the simulatability of \mathcal{T} , the difference between the games \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 is negligible. This means, $\Pr[\mathcal{G}_1 = 1] \leq \Pr[\mathcal{G}_2 = 1] + \nu_2(1^\lambda)$.

Game \mathcal{G}_3 : In this game, we output a solution to the instance inst of the hard problem if the adversary outputs a valid forgery. Between the games \mathcal{G}_2 and \mathcal{G}_3 , there is no difference in the view of the adversary. Yet, the game \mathcal{G}_3 is a reduction from the strong unforgeability of Σ to its underlying hard problem.

Claim. If the adversary outputs a valid message-forgery pair (m^*, σ^*) for \mathcal{G}_2 , this message-forgery pair allows the transparent reductions breaking algorithm $\mathcal{T}.\text{Break}$ to compute a solution for the instance inst of the underlying hard problem.

We now use Section 7 to conclude our proof. As \mathcal{G}_3 simulates StrongSigForge perfectly, if it does not abort, we now have:

$$\Pr[\text{Ext}(\lambda) = 1] \leq \Pr[\text{StrongSigForge}(\lambda) = 1] + \nu_1(1^\lambda) + \nu_2(1^\lambda).$$

We assumed that \mathcal{A} wins Ext with non-negligible probability, and thus \mathcal{A} also wins StrongSigForge with non-negligible probability. This contradicts the SUF-CMA security of Σ ; thus, such an adversary can not exist.

7.1 Adaptor Signatures from BBS^+

This section shows that the BBS^+ signature scheme [7, 2, 11] achieves all conditions of Theorem 3. The BBS^+ signature scheme is pairing-based and provably secure in the standard model, assuming the hardness of the q -SDH assumption [6]. In this section, let \mathbb{G}_1 , \mathbb{G}_2 , and \mathbb{G}_t be three cyclic groups of prime order p . Let g_0 be a generator of \mathbb{G}_1 and h_0 be a generator of \mathbb{G}_2 , such that $g_0 = \psi(h_0)$ for an efficient isomorphism $\psi : \mathbb{G}_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$ and let \tilde{e} be an efficiently computable bilinear map $\tilde{e} : \mathbb{G}_1 \times \mathbb{G}_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_t$.

Definition 7 (BBS+ Signature Scheme). Let $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$ be the security parameter, the BBS^+ signature scheme consists of the following algorithms:

$\text{Pgen}(1^\lambda)$. The public parameter generation algorithm chooses $g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{L+1} \in \mathbb{G}_1$ which are all generators of \mathbb{G}_1 and h_0 which is a generator of \mathbb{G}_2 . The elements g_i and $h_i := \psi^{-1}(g_i)$ are chosen so that the relative discrete logarithm of the generators is unknown.

$\text{KGen}(1^\lambda)$. The key generation algorithm randomly chooses $\text{sk} \in \mathbb{Z}_p^*$ and computes $\text{vk} = h_0^{\text{sk}}$. The secret key is sk , and the public key is vk .

$\text{Sign}(\text{sk}, m_0, \dots, m_L)$. To sign a tuple $(m_1, \dots, m_L) \in \mathbb{Z}_p^*$ of messages, the signing algorithm chooses a value $e \in \mathbb{Z}_p^*$ and a random number r . It then computes

$A = [g_0 \cdot g_1^r \cdot g_2^{m_1} \cdots g_{L+1}^{m_L}]^{\frac{1}{e+\text{sk}}}$. It outputs the signature $\sigma := (A, e, r)$.

$\text{Vrfy}(\text{vk}, \sigma, m)$. To verify a signature (A, e, r) on a message tuple (m_1, \dots, m_L) , the verification algorithm checks, if $\tilde{e}(A, \text{vk} \cdot h_0^e) = \tilde{e}(g_0 \cdot g_1^r \cdot g_2^{m_1} \cdots g_{L+1}^{m_L}, h_0)$.

Applying Theorem 3 to BBS^+ . The following lemmas show that BBS^+ is a dichotomic signature scheme, and its strong unforgeability can be proven using a simulatable transparent reduction. Furthermore, we show the existence of an efficient statement verification algorithm if the group \mathbb{G}_1 has efficient membership checking. We defer the proofs of the following lemmas to the full version.

Lemma 2. The BBS+ signature scheme is a dichotomic signature scheme w.r.t the homomorphic function $\text{OWF} : y \in \mathbb{Z}_p \rightarrow g_1^y \in \mathbb{G}_1$ in accordance with Definition 3.

Lemma 3. The BBS+ signature scheme is strongly unforgeable against an adaptively chosen message attack under the q -SDH assumption. This strong unforgeability can be proven using a transparent reduction.

Lemma 4. Let g_1 be a generator of \mathbb{G}_1 , and let the values $C_1, \dots, C_Q \in \mathbb{G}_1$ be randomly distributed. Let Rel be a hard relation with publicly decideable auxiliary information w.r.t the language $\mathcal{L}_{\text{Rel}} := \{(Y, \text{aux}, y) \mid y \in \mathbb{Z}_p^*, Y := g_1^y; \text{aux} := (C_1^y, \dots, C_Q^y)\}$. The transparent reduction of the SUF-CMA security of the BBS+ signature scheme is simulatable for Rel in accordance with Definition 5.

Lemma 5. If the group \mathbb{G}_1 has efficient membership testing, then there exists an efficient algorithm StmtVrfy that, on input $(\text{vk}, Y, \text{aux})$, can decide if a statement Y is an element of the image of OWF .

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